

The pH of the test solution was adjusted with $\text{HNO}_3/\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$ solution. An Elico digital pH meter was used for pH measurements. All the observations were made at room temperature $24 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 2.130 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{1/3}$. The *cis* and *trans* isomers of Co(III) complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]^+$ were prepared² by taking $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M Co}^{3+}$ ions, and their polarograms were recorded at different pH values. 1.0M Potassium chloride and 0.001% gelatin were used as supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor, respectively. The ionic strength of the test solution was kept constant at $\mu = 1.0$ (KCl).

Results and Discussion

Each of the *cis* and *trans* isomers of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]^+$ gives a single reduction wave at and above pH 10.0 for *cis* isomer and at and above pH 11.0 for *trans* isomer, respectively. However, both the isomers give a single reduction wave at and below pH 4.0. A two stage reduction is observed for both the isomers if the pH is fixed between 4-10 in the former case and 4-11 in the latter case. The two stage reduction of cobalt complexes may be due to the conversion of Co(III) complex to Co(II) complex and Co(II) complex to cobalt metal³⁻⁵. This has been confirmed by calculating the value of number of electrons 'n' involved in each electro-reduction process by millicoulometric method⁷. In all the cases the reduction of both the *cis* and *trans* isomers under study was found to be diffusion controlled as indicated by the linearity of i_a vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin.

Though both the isomers have a small decrease in their $E_{1/2}$ values at different pH values, these are separated by a little over 0.10 V at pH 4.0. This pH may, therefore, be recommended as a suitable pH for the identification of the two isomers. Further, the *cis*-isomer is reduced at a more positive potential than the *trans* form. The observed shift in the half wave potentials of the two forms is based on an argument that the preferred orientation of the *cis* complex is due to the large internal dipole at a positive surface⁸.

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Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Mn(II) by Some Uni- and Polyvalent Anions vis-a-vis the Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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IN continuation of our earlier publication¹ on the suppression of polarographic negative maximum of Mn(II) by some uni- and polyvalent cations, we report here the results of our investigation on the suppression of this maximum by some uni- and polyvalent anions viz., Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , CNS^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-} and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ vis-a-vis the kinetics of the electrode reaction.

Experimental

All the experimental details were the same as reported earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The experimental conditions such as the concentration of the depolarizer, the concentration of the supporting electrolyte (KCl), pH and the height of mercury column were adjusted in a way as to get a sharp and well-defined maximum of Mn(II) and these conditions were kept the same in all the cases. The concentration of the depolarizer was kept at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and that of the supporting electrolyte at 0.05 M, the pH of the medium was adjusted to 6.0 and the height of the mercury column (h_{corr}) was 71.45 cm.

The first kind polarographic maximum of Mn(II) under the chosen experimental conditions appears at -1.53 V (vs SCE) and lies well on the negative side of the potential of the electrocapillary zero under the same experimental conditions. Since the $E_{1/2}$ of Mn(II) also lies on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero, the maximum of Mn(II) is of negative polarity^{2a}.

A perusal of Table 1 shows that E_{max} gets shifted to positive potentials with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions. This positive shift in E_{max} can be explained as below.

Polarographic maximum of the first kind is caused by streaming of the solution from the bulk to the drop, thereby bringing the depolarizer to the electrode surface in excess of the quantity supposed to be brought by diffusion alone. Therefore, the current rises above the limiting diffusion current. This streaming is caused by motion in the inner

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NOTES

TABLE I—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Mn(II) IN THE PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF UNI- AND POLYVALENT ANIONS AT $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$[Mn^{2+}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[KCl] = 0.05 M$; $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.03 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/6}$ (in 0.05M KCl, open circuit); $h_{corr} = 71.45 \text{ cm}$

[Anion] M	$-E_{max}$ (SCE) V	$-E_{1/2}$ (SCE) V	i_{max} μA	i_0 μA	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	α	$k_{sh} \times 10^3$ cm/sec
0.0	1.53	—	15.71	—	—	—	—	—
$\times 10$								
0.5	1.53	—	15.71	—	—	—	—	—
1.5	1.52	—	10.01	—	—	—	—	—
1.7	1.51	—	8.62	—	—	—	—	—
*2.7	no max	1.490	—	7.64	40	7.11	0.80	5.63
4.3	"	1.495	—	7.23	41	6.35	0.78	5.11
6.0	"	1.497	—	6.81	48	5.64	0.74	3.90
$\times 10$								
1.6	1.53	—	10.15	—	—	—	—	—
2.0	1.52	—	8.06	—	—	—	—	—
2.3	1.51	—	7.78	—	—	—	—	—
*4.5	no max	1.494	—	7.09	40	6.11	0.78	3.14
9.3	"	1.498	—	6.67	42	5.45	0.70	1.95
13.2	"	1.500	—	6.12	47	4.55	0.63	1.30
$\times 10$								
0.5	1.53	—	14.65	—	—	—	—	—
1.1	1.52	—	10.01	—	—	—	—	—
1.7	1.51	—	8.06	—	—	—	—	—
*1.9	no max	1.486	—	7.78	40	7.37	0.82	6.24
3.9	"	1.488	—	7.09	41	6.11	0.78	4.73
5.1	"	1.490	—	6.67	42	5.41	0.76	3.88
$\times 10$								
0.4	1.53	—	11.95	—	—	—	—	—
0.9	1.52	—	10.15	—	—	—	—	—
1.2	1.51	—	8.06	—	—	—	—	—
*1.3	no max	1.483	—	7.78	40	7.37	0.83	3.88
2.1	"	1.484	—	6.95	40	5.87	0.82	3.64
2.6	"	1.485	—	6.39	41	4.97	0.80	3.12
$\times 10$								
0.3	1.53	—	15.57	—	—	—	—	—
0.7	1.52	—	11.26	—	—	—	—	—
0.9	1.51	—	9.45	—	—	—	—	—
*1.2	no max	1.487	—	7.37	40	6.60	0.84	5.31
2.9	"	1.498	—	6.81	41	5.64	0.80	3.86
4.5	"	1.497	—	6.12	42	4.55	0.70	1.73
$\times 10^3$								
2.0	1.53	—	14.46	—	—	—	—	—
4.0	1.52	—	9.03	—	—	—	—	—
4.5	1.51	—	7.64	—	—	—	—	—
*5.0	no max	1.492	—	7.37	40	6.60	0.86	2.91
11.0	"	1.497	—	6.53	41	5.19	0.82	1.69
13.0	"	1.498	—	6.25	42	4.76	0.76	1.51
$\times 10^3$								
0.8	1.52	—	8.75	—	—	—	—	—
1.0	1.52	—	8.02	—	—	—	—	—
1.4	1.51	—	7.61	—	—	—	—	—
*1.6	no max	1.500	—	7.41	44	6.69	0.87	1.73
20.0	"	1.510	—	6.75	46	5.53	0.82	0.81
32.0	"	1.514	—	6.08	47	4.49	0.81	0.59
$\times 10^3$								
0.6	1.53	—	12.65	—	—	—	—	—
0.8	1.52	—	8.62	—	—	—	—	—
1.0	1.52	—	7.78	—	—	—	—	—
*1.2	no max	1.492	—	7.64	40	6.78	0.88	3.87
6.4	"	1.508	—	7.37	42	6.60	0.86	2.65
12.8	"	1.510	—	6.95	46	5.87	0.76	1.31
$\times 10^4$								
1.0	1.53	—	9.03	—	—	—	—	—
2.0	1.52	—	7.37	—	—	—	—	—
3.0	1.51	—	6.81	—	—	—	—	—
*4.0	no max	1.480	—	6.53	46	5.19	0.90	2.17
6.0	"	1.488	—	6.12	49	4.55	0.84	2.09

* Concentration at which the maximum gets just suppressed.

layers of mercury. The dropping electrode is not homogeneously polarized when current passes and a potential difference arises along its surface. The difference of potential on the surface in turn brings about a change in the surface tension responsible for the motion of the mercury. Surface active substances added to the solution are adsorbed on the mercury surface and are taken to the place of greatest surface tension both by the motion of the mercury as well as the adhering solution. Thus they accumulate there and decrease the surface tension, curbing the streaming and consequently the maximum. This happens so when the mean potential of the electrode reaches the electrocapillary zero where the differences in the surface tension are equilibrated, stopping the motion of the mercury.

The adsorptive anions (like those used here) shift the electrocapillary maximum to less negative potentials^{2b} (positive shift) and deform the negative side of the electrocapillary parabola so that the surface tension for any applied potential is lower than the one in the absence of these ions. In other words, for the same surface tension a lower applied potential is needed. Thus, if any such adsorptive anion is successful in suppressing a negative maximum of the first kind, a gradual positive shift of the maximum prior to the final suppression seems to be a necessary prerequisite. Malik and Haque³ observed that the efficacy of a suppressor decreases as the distance of the maximum from the electrocapillary zero increases. Since the addition of adsorptive anions causes a positive shift of the electrocapillary zero, the positive shift of the maximum by the addition of these ions on the way to the final elimination of the maximum is consistent with the observation of Malik and Haque.

After the suppression of the maximum by the requisite amounts of uni- and polyvalent anions, Mn(II) yields, in each case, a well-defined and diffusion-controlled wave as is shown by the linearity of i_d vs $\sqrt{t_{0.01}}$ plots and their passing through the origin.

Influence of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions on the kinetics of the quasi-reversible electrode reaction of Mn(II) :

A perusal of the slope values (Table 1) of log plots shows that the slope values of 2-electron reduction process of Mn(II) lie in the range 40-49 mV which indicate⁴⁻⁸ that the polarographic reduction of Mn(II) is quasi-reversible in presence of increasing amounts of uni- and polyvalent anions. The values of the kinetic parameters (α and k_{sh}) of the quasi-reversible electrode reaction of Mn(II) have been calculated by Gellings' method⁹. The values of k_{sh} are of the magnitude of 10^{-3} cm/sec which confirm^{10,11} the quasi-reversible nature of the electrode reaction of Mn(II). It is observed that the value of k_{sh} decreases with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions. This shows that the quasi-reversible electrode reaction of Mn(II) tends towards irreversibility with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions. From Table

1 it is also evident that the value of α decreases with increasing concentrations of the anions thereby showing that the quasi-reversible electrode reaction of Mn(II) tends towards irreversibility. Thus, the changes in the values of k_{sh} and α lead to the same conclusion. Further, a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ and a decrease in i_d with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions lend support to the conclusion arrived at on the basis of the changes in the values of k_{sh} and α .

Relative efficacies of uni- and polyvalent anions in the suppression of the maximum of Mn(II) on the basis of α values :

At the stage where the maximum of Mn(II) just disappears, the order in the value of α (Table 1) signifies¹² the extent to which the addition of uni- and polyvalent anions shifts the electrode reaction of Mn(II) towards irreversibility from the position in the absence of the anions. In other words a suppressing anion for which α has a higher value at the point of just suppression will be more effective with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Mn(II). On this basis the order of efficacies of various uni- and polyvalent anions has been established as $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} > \text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-} > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{CNS}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{I}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^-$.

It is interesting to note that uni- and polyvalent anions follow the valency rule. Further, the order of relative efficacies found on the basis of α values in respect of uni- and polyvalent anions is identical with that obtained on the basis of molarity scale.

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